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Results from the operation of the first industrial size biogas-fed SOFC plant in Europe

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Abstract

The EU-funded DEMOSOFC project (www.demosofc.eu), currently running, has spent the last 4 years in demonstrating the technical and economic feasibility of operating an industrial-size SOFC system (100 kW_e, 2x50 kW_e modules) in a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). The fuel for the SOFC modules is biogas, which is available on-site from the anaerobic digestion of sludge collected from the treated wastewater. A heat-recovery loop allows to recover useful thermal energy from the hot SOFC exhaust gases (90 kW_{th}), transferred through a water loop to the sludge.

The plant includes 2 SOFC modules started respectively in October 2017 and October 2018. The first SOFC module has reached more than 5500 hours of operation on site (+1000 at Convion facilities) and the second SOFC module more than 9800 hours. Results from the operation of these modules confirmed the expected high-level performance of the fuel cell system: average measured SOFC efficiency from compressed biogas to AC power is 49-50%, with peaks at 56% at partial power (40 kW_e).

A dedicated emissions measurements campaign has been performed in December 2017. Results show no NO_x (detection limit of the method 20 mg/m³) or SO₂ (d.l. 8 mg/m³) and particulate lower than ambient air values (< 0.01 mg/m³).

A deep economic analysis has been also performed, together with the plant owner SMAT s.p.a., to understand the current site preparation and the potential reduction of a second replication, thanks to the lesson-learned from the demonstration site. A total potential reduction of costs of 56% could be achieved according to the analysis performed.

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Introduction

The DEMOSOFC plant [1] is the first industrial-size Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) system installed in a real site in Europe, and fed by biogas from waste water treatment. Industrial-size fuel cell systems, usually Molten Carbonate Fuel Cells (MCFCs) are already available outside Europe, especially in USA [2], Japan and South Korea [3], but not yet in EU. Key advantages of fuel cell based industrial systems in biogas plants have been deeply demonstrated in the authors' previous works [4]–[8] and include:

- High efficiency increase with respect to traditional biogas-fed Internal Combustion Engines (ICEs), especially for low-medium size systems. ICEs usually show electrical efficiency ranging from 35-38% to 43% [9], when the plant size increases from tens of kW to MW size. SOFC systems can indeed provide values higher than 55% from few kW to MW size.
- Zero emissions to atmosphere in terms of NO_x, SO_x, VOC and PM, which are traditionally a criticality in standard combustion engine (many ICEs need the installation of post-combustors to comply with local strict rules on emissions).

The scientific and research activity of the DEMOSOFC project focused on the analysis of the performance and management of the entire demo, including the biogas purification system (specifically designed for FC applications in the framework of the project), on the economics of the plant and on the replication potential in the EU area.

1. The DEMOSOFC plant layout

The DEMOSOFC site WWTP is located in Collegno, in the Torino premises (IT). The Collegno plant has a nominal capacity of 250'000 Person Equivalent (P.E.) and it is currently serving around 180'000 P.E., both residential and industrial.

Figure 1. DEMOSOFC plant layout.

The plant is using the as-produced biogas for electrical and thermal energy production in a SOFC-based cogeneration system. The DEMOSOFC plant comprises of three main sections: 1) the biogas clean-up and compression section, 2) the SOFC power modules, and 3) the heat recovery loop. Figure 1 shows a schematic layout of the WWTP process and its integration with the DEMOSOFC plant.

Biogas clean-up and compression section

The biogas clean-up system aims at removing trace compounds (mainly sulphur and silicon based) from the raw biogas, since they could be detrimental for the SOFC module (both for the reformer catalyst and the FC anode). Required purification level, given by the

SOFC producer and used to design the cleaning unit, were max. 30 ppb of total Sulphur (including H₂S) and 10 ppb if siloxanes.

The system includes also other components like blowers and chillers to flow the gas until the DEMOSOFC area and remove condensing water; furthermore, a compressor is installed to provide inlet biogas to the SOFC at 4 bar(g), as requested by the SOFC manufacturer (Figure 2). A more detailed description of the cleaning section is available in [10]. The biogas cleaning and compression section (Biokomp, [11]) has been designed after a one-year monitoring of biogas composition in Collegno, where H₂S (average 20 ppm) and siloxanes (average 1 ppm) have been detected as the most harmful components to be removed. An in-line and real-time gas analysis (supplied by Qualvista LTD [12]) is installed to monitor the removal efficiency of the biogas clean-up unit. The online gas sensor can detect continuously both macro-composition (CH₄, CO₂, O₂) and contaminants (H₂S and total Silicon).

Figure 2. Biogas cleaning and compression section layout.

SOFC Modules

The core of the DEMOSOFC plant are the SOFC units supplied by Convion Oy [13], partner of the DEMOSOFC project. The modules can provide up to 55% electrical efficiency and 30% thermal efficiency.

Figure 3. SOFC modules and the DEMOSOFC site.

The two SOFC modules (Figure 3) produce around 100 kW_e, which cover around 25-30% of the WWTP electrical consumption [6]. The SOFC units are fed by biogas during nominal operation and are connected to the heat recovery system (water-glycol loop). Compressed air is required during start-up and an N-H mixture (95% N₂, 5% H₂) is available for standby

operation (maximum 24 hours maintenance on the biogas line – e.g. compressor maintenance – with the SOFC system in hot stand-by, avoiding shutdown).

Heat Recovery Section

Heat recovered from the SOFC units is completely transferred to the sludge entering the anaerobic digester through an intermediate water-glycol loop (30% glycol in water). Circulation pumps (twin pumps to avoid stops during maintenance) and three-way valves for regulation have been installed and a new sludge-water heat exchanger is supporting the existing one.

The DEMOSOFC plant has been in operation since October 2017 and the project will end in October 2020. During the 3 years of operation the DEMO site has reached in total more than 13'700 hours of operation with SOFC 1 or 2 running (1'500 hours only were performed with two modules in parallel). The following chapter aims to analyze results from the operation of the entire system, including the biogas cleaning unit and the overall DEMO site performance.

2. Results

Biogas raw composition is measured once per day by the online Qualvista analyzer (sample #3 in Figure 2). Clean biogas (both between and after the *lead-and-lag* reactors, respectively sample#1 and sample #2 in Figure 2) is indeed measured continuously for the other hours of the day. Each measurement (performed in batch mode) takes 40 minutes and N₂ is flushed after raw gas analysis. Results on the raw biogas composition (in terms of contaminants) are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Raw biogas micro-composition (H₂S and total Silicon).

Figure 5. Methane content in raw biogas.

H₂S level has always been in line with historical trends with an average value of 26 ppm (min 0 ppm – max 71 ppm). Siloxanes are also varying in a limited range with an average value in of 3.6 mg/m³ (min 0 mg/m³ – max 9.4 mg/m³). Variation in the sulphur levels can be detected during the different operation periods: this is due to fluctuations in the iron chloride dosing in the water line (iron oxide is used to precipitate phosphorus, but it also reduces the sulfur content in the water). Siloxanes indeed shows some seasonal variations

[14]–[16]. Average methane content in the same period has been 64% (min 56% - max 72%). Methane content is stable on an hourly basis while weekly-monthly variations have been detected. Anyway, the SOFC was continuously monitoring the methane level (with a second continuous and fast-response sensor installed close to the main gas analyzer) and was able to keep the power output stable despite the fluctuations.

During the entire analyzed period, until today, no breakthrough of contaminants has been detected by the gas analyzer. The main reason for this is the under-utilization of the system compared to the design stage: the cleaning unit was designed for 3 SOFC modules running in parallel while, during the project, except for 1500 hours with 2 modules in parallel, only one module per time was in operation with a capacity factor between 40 and 60%.

A further analysis has been performed to compare the current loaded sulphur and silicon on the cleaning vessels with the maximum loading rate measured in the experimental phase during the design of the cleaning system. For what concerns H₂S, the adsorption capacity measured in the laboratory (in conditions similar to the site ones but with simulated gas) was around 84 mgS/g (expressed as mass of sulphur on mass of sorbent), while the current loaded sulphur amounts to 7.4 kg. Looking at only the first vessel in the series (Figure 2), filled with 250 kg of sorbent, only 35% of the potential loading capacity has been exploited. The same calculation can be performed with silicon (estimated adsorption capacity was 151 mgSi/g and loaded amount is 0.67 kg): in this case the exploited loading capacity amounts to only 1.8%.

Sulphur will thus probably be the first component reaching the breakthrough (as expected from the lower adsorption capacity of the sulphur-dedicated sorbents) but the system still seems far from the sorbent replacement activity.

Figure 6. Electric and total efficiencies of the first Convion C50 SOFC system as function of the electrical net power output and corresponding normalized distributions. a) Electric (red squares) and total (black crosses) efficiency mean values for electrical net power output segments during stable operation. Segments are represented by the vertical dashed lines. Black dashed and dotted lines represent second order polynomial fits of the electric and total efficiencies for electrical net power output values greater zero. b) Normalized distribution of the electrical net power output. c) Normalized distribution of the electric and total efficiencies. Combined standard uncertainties were around 3% for the electric and around 6% for the total efficiency. [17]

For what concerns the SOFC modules, the 1st one was started in October 2017 and has now reached 5500+ hours of operation onsite (plus 1000 hours at Convion facilities during

the testing phase), while the 2nd was started in October 2018 and has reached 9800+ hours of operation onsite.

A detailed analysis of the SOFC modules operation has been performed and is available in [17]. This analysis was performed in late 2019 and was related to 9113 hours of operation, in which the modules provided electricity and heat to the plant. Results are here shown for what concerns only the 1st SOFC module (called SOFC1). Figure 6 shows the performance of the SOFC1. In Fig. 2a) the total electric efficiency and the total efficiency as a function of the electric net power output from 0 to 55 kW_e are illustrated. The SOFC system was operated stable in an electric net power output range between 25 kW_e and 55 kW_e. In this range the electric efficiency stayed stable between 50% and 55%. The black crosses show the total efficiency mean values which were between 67% and 87% during stable operation. The stable and high electric efficiencies over the operating net power output range (25–55 kW_e) illustrate an advantage of fuel cell technology in comparison to micro turbines and internal combustion engines. The results show that power modulation according to the site demand is possible while maintaining high efficiencies using SOFC systems. For most of the time (79%) the electric efficiency was between 50% and 55%. Around 2% of the time the electric efficiency was even higher with values between 55% and 60%.

Another analysis performed on the SOFC modules is the one related to the efficiency trend over time. Electrical and total efficiency for SOFC1 during year 2018 are shown in Figure 7. During the first two operating periods (from April to June and some days in August), the power output was kept stable at 53 kW_e electrical.

Figure 7. Efficiency of SOFC1 during 2018.

During this period, electrical efficiency was showing very good performance in the range 48 to 55%, with average values around 50-52% (electrical efficiency is here defined as net value from compressed biogas to AC power). Total efficiency shows an increase during time since the heat recovery system has been strongly optimized, comparing to the start-up phase, trying to maximize the thermal recovery; for this reason, thermal efficiency shows values up to 90% in the last part of the first operating period and in the second one. No efficiency degradation is visible from the graph shown. During the third operating period (September-October 2018) the system was operated at partial load for all the time (28 kW_e) and the efficiency shows an increase up to values close to 60%, while total

efficiency decreased a little bit due to the different thermal management within the SOFC module at partial load.

The two SOFC systems had cell stacks from two different suppliers, both representing the state of the art at the time of the design process. Cell voltage degradation, which is not reported here in quantitative terms because of confidentiality rights, is always a result of combined and cumulative effects of operational hours, operating profile and thermal cycles as well as potential influence of impurities. In steady operation, witnessed stack voltage degradation rate logged in field conditions with biogas was equal to that measured by the manufacturers in their test bench operation, indicating both design and operational success of the system and gas cleaning set-up. In post-mortem analysis of replaced stacks, anodes were found in good condition and proving that no breakthroughs of sulfur or siloxanes had taken place. Total rate of degradation including impact of thermal cycles was clearly higher than steady state degradation as operating history of stacks was particularly aggressive in the early stages of their lifetime. Towards the end of their useful lifetime, spread of voltages increased as a result of degradation and partial replacement of stacks in operation, limiting maneuverability of a system consisting of a large number of stacks exhibiting different voltage response to loading. This heterogenous condition was a reason behind downrating of power output at later stages.

Total electrical production from the DEMOSOFC plant was equal to 537 MWh, while thermal production was 356 MWh: all the energy produced was self-consumed within the plant. With the prices paid by the WWTP for electricity and heat, this is equal to a saving of more than 72'500€ for what concerning electricity and 21'900€ for what concerning saved natural gas from the grid. Average capacity factors (defined as the hours with SOFC modules on over the total project time) have been 43.5% for SOFC1 and 61% for SOFC2. Shutdown periods were due to authorization issues at the beginning (being a first-of-its-kind plant, local authority and grid operators requested more time to approve the authorization), together with instabilities in the cleaning system and heat recovery unit (solved by optimizing, during the first months, the operation and the control of these section). Later, during the stable operation, the long lead times for SOFC module maintenance were the main reasons for long shut down periods lowering the overall availability SOFC maintenance.

Section	Number of incidents
Clean-up section	4
SOFC modules	8
Control system & other sections	4
Gas analyser	1
Authorization process	2

Table 1. Number of incidents at the DEMOSOFC site. Not all the unexpected incidents caused a shutdown and lead time for maintenance/repair of the problems have been between few hours and different months.

During the operation of the SOFC modules, an analysis of the auxiliary equipment has been performed, to understand the impact of these components on the overall plant efficiency. Results are shown in Figure 8. The total auxiliary consumption with one SOFC module running (including all the biogas treatment section, heat recovery, electrical and control parts, conditioning of the technical building, etc.) is around 11.72 kW. The value is dominated by the biogas treatment section (two chillers, blower, compressor) and all the equipment within the container (especially ventilation and cooling during Summer). The two sections together account for 77% of the consumption, followed by small contributions of other components (the contribution of all the other section is always lower than 5%). An optimized design for future biogas-SOFC replications should thus focus on the biogas processing system. In quantitative terms, auxiliaries are currently counting for more than

20% on the electrical production but this is due to the off-design operation of the site (designed for 3 SOFC modules, 58 kW each) when working with 1 SOFC system only. Considering 174 kW total electrical production (design conditions) auxiliary are expected to impact for less than 10%.

Figure 8. Auxiliary components for the DEMOSOFC site.

VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland [18], partner of the DEMOSOFC project, has performed onsite emissions analysis at the DEMOSOFC plant on December 7th, 2017. Results are shown in Figure 9 and discussed in detail in [17]. Results show that NO_x, SO₂, HCl, HF and organic compounds are all below the instrumentation detection limits see details in [10], [17], [19]). Particulate matter analysis (Figure 9) shows that particulate concentration in the surrounding ambient air is higher than the one in the SOFC module exhaust gases: the system is indeed filtering inlet ambient air and a ultra-low amount of particulate is added by the process.

Figure 9. Results of the emissions analysis at the DEMOSOFC site (courtesy of VTT [18]).

A final evaluation was performed on the costs experienced during the DEMOSOFC project for what concerns the site preparation, defined as all the required components to be installed in order to run the SOFC modules. Results are shown in Table 2 and have been presented in [20]. Site preparation costs can be divided into mechanical works (piping, valves, sensors, etc.), electrical works (wires, power supply, control system, meters, etc.), civil works (basement preparation, pipe racks, technical buildings, etc.), biogas cleaning works (blower, chiller, container with compressor, chiller, cleaning vessel, etc.), auxiliary works (biogas analyzer, gas cylinders, gas cylinders box, etc.). The total cost for the site preparation during the DEMOSOFC project has been more than 850 k€, which account for around 4'500€/kW (considering the design system size of 174 kW). In order to reduce the impact of the site preparation on the overall plant cost, an optimization analysis was performed by the engineers from Politecnico di Torino and SMAT s.p.a responsible for the site construction.

The analysis focused primarily on the following elements:

- Excluding all the site-dependent costs (for example the WWTP needed a new electrical cabinet to host the CHP system, or the need of a blower because the plant was located far from the digester).
- Moving from underground pipeline to external (covered) pipeline.
- Removal of twin pumps (currently installed for guaranteeing a continuous operation even in case of pumps maintenance)
- Reduction of UPS size (currently over-sized for hours of operation, but required only for less than a second)
- Simplification of the technical building (moving to a simplified containerized solution)
- Optimization of the cleaning system (reduction of the number of vessels)

By means of these modifications the total costs could be reduced of 56% (with a specific impact close to 2'000 €/kW): the higher reductions are possible in the civil and mechanical works section. Furthermore, it should be underlined that this analysis is performed for a new construction, while many biogas plants already have a CHP unit and so many of these costs could be avoided.

	DEMOSOFC cost (€)	Optimized cost (€)	Reduction (%)
Mechanical works	174'562	65'502	-63%
Electrical works	173'913	100'819	-42%
Civil works	191'920	23'758	-88%
Biogas cleaning works	221'087	132'652	-40%
Auxiliary works	91'677	54'597	-40%
Total Costs	853'159	377'328	-56%

Table 2. DEMOSOFC site preparation costs in the current and optimized scenarios.

3. Conclusions

The DEMOSOFC plant has been in operation since October 2017 with 2 SOFC modules running (50 kW_e electrical each). During the 3 years of operation the DEMO site has reached in total more than 13'700 hours of operation with SOFC 1 or 2 running (capacity factor has been between 40 and 60% for SOFC1 and SOFC2 respectively). Shutdown periods were due to the authorization process in the first year of operation, followed by some unexpected maintenance on the cleaning system and the SOFC modules.

The presents work showed results from the operation of the entire system, including the biogas cleaning unit and the overall DEMO site performance, followed by economic perspectives.

The DEMOSOFC plant was able to demonstrate the possibility of operating an SOFC system within an industrial environment, fed by biogas from WWTP, keeping high electrical efficiency around 50% and total efficiency above 85%. Therefore, the efficiency targets connected to SOFC systems have been validated.

Biogas cleaning system and thermal recovery unit, after some months of optimization of the control, were found to be robust and reliable, and their design could be improved to reduce the costs.

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